

Numerical evaluation of multivariate power curves for wind turbines in wakes using nacelle lidars

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ABSTRACT

The IEC standards describe how to measure the power performance of an isolated wake-free wind turbine. However, most wind turbines operate under waked conditions for a substantial amount of time, calling for the need of a new methodology for power performance evaluation. We define multivariate power curves in the form of multivariate polynomial regressions, whose input variables are several wind speed and turbulence measurements retrieved with nacelle lidars. We use a dataset of synthetic power performance tests including both waked and wake-free conditions. The dataset is generated through aeroelastic simulations combined with both virtual nacelle lidars and the dynamic wake meandering model. A feature-selection algorithm is used to select the input variables among the available measurements, showing that the optimal model includes four input variables: three correspondent to wind speed and one to turbulence measures. Additionally, we give insights on the optimal nacelle-lidar scanning geometry needed to implement the multivariate power curve. Results show that the multivariate power curves predict the power output with accuracy of the same order under both waked and wake-free operation. For the in-wake cases, the accuracy is much higher than that of the IEC standard power curve, with an error reduction of up to 88%.

1. Introduction

For many years, the power output of a wind turbine was defined as function of two flow characteristics: the air density and the wind speed at hub height [1]. However, several studies have shown that additional variables should be considered when evaluating the power performance of a wind turbine, e.g. turbulence characteristics and vertical wind shear [2–4]. Clifton and Wagner [2] investigated the effect of atmospheric turbulence on the power output of a wind turbine through aeroelastic simulations and showed that turbulence and power are closely related for wind speeds just above the cut-in and just below the rated value. Specifically, the power output increases with turbulence around cut-in, while it decreases close to rated. The same effect was shown with measurements by Hedevang [5] and Bardal and Sætran [4]. Wagner et al. [3] evaluated the effect of the vertical wind shear on the power output. They showed that one single velocity measurement at hub height does not accurately estimate the kinetic energy flux through the rotor. Therefore, they introduced a methodology to increase the accuracy of the power curve by using wind speed measurements from several heights combined into one scalar quantity, the rotor equivalent wind speed.

Research on the effect of turbulence and vertical wind shear led to the revision of the International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC)

standard for power performance testing. In the most recent version, both turbulence intensity and wind shear are included as variables to be considered when testing power curves [6]. However, the IEC standard power curves still provide a rather simplified evaluation of the power performance and require further improvements. One of the main issues, portrayed also in its newest edition, is that the IEC standard only describes the methodology to assess the power performance of an isolated, wake-free wind turbine. However, most wind turbines are currently clustered together within wind farms and operate under waked conditions for a substantial amount of time. This means that these wind turbines operate without an accurate indication of their power performance under their actual operating conditions. This is not only true for the waked wind turbines. Due to blockage effects, the performance of the non-waked wind turbines in a wind farm are also affected as shown by Sebastiani et al. [7]. Therefore, there is a need to implement an alternative methodology for power performance evaluation, which is reliable under waked conditions or complex inflow in general.

Several previous works have introduced alternative methods to model the power curve of a wind turbine. In some, the power output was modelled as function of the wind speed at hub height through both parametric and non-parametric models [8–11]. In others, the

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power performance was modelled through multivariate power curves accounting for several atmospheric variables, such as turbulence, vertical wind shear and wind veer [12–15]. Some other studies included control variables as the turbine's rotational speed and pitch angle of the blades [16,17]. Additionally, Sebastiani et al. [18] used trivariate power curves accounting for wind speed, turbulence and yaw misalignment. In many of these studies, only one wind speed measurement was considered [8–11,16,17], while others used wind speeds at several heights to characterize the vertical wind shear [12–15]. However, none of the studies included more than one wind speed measurement at the same height, which could be beneficial under waked conditions. Additionally, none of the available studies specifically focused on waked conditions.

In this work, we test multivariate power curves, which include several wind speed and turbulence measurements retrieved through nacelle-mounted lidars. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first evaluation of multivariate power curves in wakes using nacelle lidars. The main objective is to evaluate the power performance of a wind turbine with the same accuracy under both waked and free-standing conditions. We define multivariable power curves in the form of multivariate polynomial regressions, whose input variables are both wind speed and turbulence measurements at several locations in front of the rotor. We test several lidar configurations, with a varying number (from 6 to 400) of wind speed measurements. A feature-selection algorithm is used to select the optimal number of measurements needed to evaluate the power performance, as well as to give insights about the best measurement locations. The analysis is conducted on a dataset of synthetic power performance measurements, which is built with the combination of aeroelastic simulations and virtual nacelle lidar measurements. We use the dynamic wake meandering (DWM) model [19] to generate waked inflows and simulate power performance measurements in wake.

This paper is organized as follows. The methodology is outlined in Section 2, with descriptions of the homogeneous turbulent wind fields in Section 2.1, the DWM model in Section 2.2 and the lidar simulator in Section 2.3. In Section 2.4, we describe how the aeroelastic simulations are combined with the virtual lidars and the DWM model to generate a dataset of virtual power performance tests. The implementation of the multivariate power curves is described in Section 2.5. Results from the analysis for wake-free and waked conditions are shown in Sections 3.1 and 3.2, respectively. The combination of both conditions is shown in Section 3.3, while the optimal lidar scanning configuration is described in Section 3.4. Finally, discussion and conclusions are presented in Sections 4 and 5, respectively.

2. Methodology

We use the DTU in-house aeroelastic code HAWC2 [20] to perform aeroelastic simulations of the Vestas V52 wind turbine [21], which has a rated power of 850 kW and rotor diameter (D) of 52 m. Additionally, we implement a lidar simulator to retrieve virtual nacelle lidar measurements from the same turbulent wind fields, which are used as input to the aeroelastic simulations. The combination of the power output from the HAWC2 simulations and the virtual measurements from the lidar simulator results in a dataset of virtual power performance measurements. Specifically, the dataset is divided in two distinct parts, consisting of power performance measurements under homogeneous and waked conditions, respectively; the wake fields are simulated with the DWM model.

2.1. Turbulence spectral model

We use three-dimensional homogeneous turbulent wind fields generated with the turbulence spectral model by Mann [22], hereafter referred to as Mann model. The three-dimensional wind field is described by the vector field $\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x})$, as time dependency is neglected because of

the Taylor's frozen turbulence hypothesis. The velocity vector field $\mathbf{u} = (u, v, w)$ consists of the along-wind (u), transverse (v) and vertical (w) components, with the along-wind component aligned with the x direction of the right-hand coordinate system $\mathbf{x} = (x, y, z)$, as shown in Fig. 2. Assuming homogeneous turbulence and no vertical wind speed, the mean velocity field results in $\langle \mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}) \rangle = (U(z), 0, 0)$, where the wind speed variation with height depends on the vertical shear.

The second-order statistics of the homogeneous three-dimensional wind field can be described with the spectral tensor $\Phi(\mathbf{k})$, which is the Fourier transform of the covariance tensor $\mathbf{R}(\mathbf{r})$, where \mathbf{r} is the separation vector and $\mathbf{k} = (k_1, k_2, k_3)$ is the vector field representing the wavenumbers along the (x, y, z) directions. The Mann model describes the spectral tensor Φ as function of three parameters: $\alpha \epsilon^{2/3}$ is the product between the Kolmogorov constant α and the turbulent energy dissipation rate ϵ , Γ is a parameter related to the anisotropy of the turbulence field, and L is a length scale related to the size of the turbulence eddies.

In this work, all the three-dimensional turbulent wind fields are generated with $L = 29.4$ m and $\Gamma = 3.9$, which are the values suggested in the IEC standard [23], while $\alpha \epsilon^{2/3}$ is varied according to the desired level of atmospheric turbulence. All the wind fields have the maximum number of grid points allowed in HAWC2: $(N_x, N_y, N_z) = (8192, 64, 64)$.

2.2. Dynamic wake meandering model

The DWM model simulates wind turbine wakes in a time domain at a relatively low computational expense. It relies on Taylor's frozen turbulence assumption and consists of three elements: a model of the quasi-steady velocity deficit and its evolution downstream; a model of the wake meandering due to large-scale turbulence structures, and a model of the wake-generated turbulence [19].

The definition of the quasi-steady velocity deficit is strongly inspired by the work of Ainslie [24]. The wake deficit in the near-wake region (within 2–3D) is defined by the turbine's axial induction derived from blade element momentum (BEM) theory [19]. In the far-wake region (downstream distances larger than 2–3D), the wake evolution is described by the thin shear layer approximation of the rotationally symmetric Navier–Stokes (N–S) equations, with the pressure terms disregarded and an eddy viscosity term used for turbulence closure [19]. The eddy viscosity ν_t accounts for both atmospheric and shear layer generated turbulence through the formulation by Keck et al. [25]:

$$\nu_t = F_1 k_1 \text{TI}_{amb} + F_2 k_2 \max \left(\frac{R_w^2}{U_{hub} R} \left| \frac{\partial U}{\partial R} \right|; \frac{R_w}{R} \left(1 - \frac{U_{min}}{U_{hub}} \right) \right), \quad (1)$$

where R_w is the wake radius, R is the rotor radius, TI_{amb} is the ambient turbulence intensity, U_{min} is the minimum wind speed in the wake and U_{hub} is the free-stream velocity at hub height. F_1 and F_2 are filter functions used to model the development of the turbulent stresses inside the wake. k_1 and k_2 are empirical constants. In our work, we use the HAWC2 default values for F_1, F_2, k_1 and k_2 .

In the DWM model, the wake is assumed as a passive tracer driven by large-scale turbulence structures. Trujillo et al. [26] showed that the atmospheric turbulence structures responsible for the wake meandering are in the order of 2D and larger. Therefore, in the DWM model, the wake meandering is modelled by superimposing turbulence fluctuations with a cut-off frequency of $f_{cut} = \frac{U}{2D}$. Those turbulence fluctuations are modelled with a Mann-model generated turbulence box, which presents a discretization of $\Delta y = \Delta z = D$ and where the velocity vectors at each grid point represent the average over the grid cube.

In addition to the atmospheric turbulence and the apparent turbulence due to the meandering of the wake, additional turbulence is generated in the wake as a consequence of the velocity shear, as well as of trailing vortices generated at both tip and root of the blade. Wake-generated turbulence tends to be isotropic and characterized by smaller structures than atmospheric turbulence [27]. Therefore,

Fig. 1. Illustration of the numerical framework utilized to generate the dataset of virtual power performance measurements.

additional wake turbulence is modelled by super-imposing a Mann-model turbulence box generated with $\Gamma = 0$ and a length scale L which is 10% of the atmospheric turbulence length scale. Additionally, wake turbulence is purely mechanically generated and rather inhomogeneous. In the DWM, the inhomogeneity of wake-generated turbulence is modelled by scaling the wake turbulence box with the factor

$$K_{m1}(\hat{r}) = |1 - \hat{U}_{def}(\hat{r})| k_{m1} + \left| \frac{\partial \hat{U}_{def}(\hat{r})}{\partial \hat{r}} \right| k_{m2}, \quad (2)$$

where \hat{U}_{def} is the axisymmetric wake velocity $U_{def} = U_{amb} - \Delta U$ nondimensionalized with U_{hub} . \hat{r} is the radial distance normalized by the rotor radius. k_{m1} and k_{m2} are empirical constants [19]. We use the HAWC2 default values for both k_{m1} and k_{m2} .

The final three-dimensional velocity field is obtained through linear superposition of the quasi steady velocity deficit, the meandering turbulence and the wake-generated turbulence to the homogeneous ambient velocity field:

$$u_{DWM} = U_{def} + u'_{amb} + u'_{meandering} + K_{m1} u'_{wake} \quad (3)$$

2.3. Nacelle lidar simulator

We implement a lidar simulator to retrieve virtual nacelle lidar measurements from the same turbulent velocity fields used as input to the aeroelastic simulations. As shown in Fig. 2, the forward-looking lidar is located in the centre of the (y, z) plane and scans the inflow approaching the wind turbine. We simulate continuous-wave (CW) lidars using a typical weighting function $\varphi(s)$, which allows us to model the lidar probe-volume effect [28]:

$$\varphi(s) = \frac{1}{\pi} \frac{z_r}{z_r^2 + s^2}, \quad \text{with } z_r = \frac{\lambda f_d^2}{\pi r_b^2}, \quad (4)$$

where z_r is the Rayleigh length, λ is the laser wavelength, r_b is the lens aperture radius, f_d is the focus distance and s is the distance from the focus point along the lidar beam direction.

In this work, we assume $\lambda = 1565$ nm and $r_b = 28$ mm, which are common values among available CW lidars. In order to provide a realistic modelling of the probe-volume effect without requiring a critically large wind field, we model the weighting functions over distances of $\pm 6z_r$ around the focus point, accounting for around 90% of the weight.

We test different scanning configurations, comprising both commercial and research lidars, as shown in Fig. 3. Specifically, we simulate the DTU SpinnerLidar [29], which retrieves 400 measurements every 2

s along the rose pattern of Fig. 3(a). Additionally, we simulate a 6-beam lidar and a circular scanning lidar. The 6-beam configuration is chosen as it is the optimal configuration for turbulence measurements [30], while the circular configuration is chosen as it is performed by one of the available commercial lidars for power performance tests. We also include a grid of ‘sonic anemometers’, which are able to retrieve the true wind and turbulence characteristics, without being affected by neither the volume averaging nor the method used to reconstruct the wind, as most lidars are.

The lidar virtual measurements consist in the retrieval of the Doppler radial velocity spectrum as

$$S(v_r, t) = \int_{s_{min}}^{s_{max}} \varphi(s) \delta(v_r - \mathbf{u}(s) \cdot \mathbf{n}) ds, \quad (5)$$

where v_r is the velocity component along the beam (radial velocity), $\mathbf{n} = (n_x, n_y, n_z)$ is the unit vector along the beam direction and δ is the Dirac delta function. Eq. (5) can be considered as a weighted histogram distribution of v_r within the probe volume. We use a discretization of 0.1 m/s for the histogram distribution in order to match the typical velocity resolution of a real lidar system. The measured radial velocity is the first statistical moment of the Doppler spectrum:

$$v_r(t) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} v_r S(v_r, t) dv_r. \quad (6)$$

Here, the along-wind component u of the velocity vector is retrieved from the radial velocity by neglecting the contribution of both the transverse v and vertical w components:

$$u = \frac{v_r}{n_x}. \quad (7)$$

In order to get information about turbulence, the radial velocity variance $\sigma_{v_r}^2$ is obtained as the second central moment of the ensemble averaged Doppler spectrum $\mathbf{S}(v_r) = \langle S(v_r, t) \rangle$:

$$\sigma_{v_r}^2 = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \mathbf{S}(v_r) (v_r - \bar{v}_r)^2 dv_r, \quad (8)$$

where \bar{v}_r is the first central moment of $\mathbf{S}(v_r)$, i.e., the mean radial velocity. This ensures that $\sigma_{v_r}^2$ is not affected by turbulence filtering due to the lidar spatial averaging [31].

When we face conditions in which the turbulent wind field is free of wakes, i.e., when the turbulent inflow is homogeneous, the components of the Reynolds stress tensor (variances and covariances of the velocity components) are estimated from the radial velocity variances $\sigma_{v_r}^2$ of the different lidar beams following the methodology described by Fu et al. [32].

Fig. 2. Illustrative three-dimensional view of one of the simulated scanning patterns, the turbine rotor and the along-wind velocity component.

Fig. 3. Nacelle lidar scanning configurations: (a) SpinnerLidar focused at 2D; (b) 6-beam lidar focused at 2D; (c) circular scanning lidar focused at 2D; (d) grid of ‘sonic anemometers’. The rotor is highlighted in black.

2.4. Generation of the dataset

As shown in Fig. 1, we combine HAWC2 with the DWM model and the lidar simulator to generate two datasets of virtual power performance tests: one consisting of wake-free homogeneous cases and the other of waked inflows, hereafter referred to as the wake-free and waked-inflow datasets. For the retrieval of 10-min statistics of both power output and wind characteristics, all the wind turbulent fields have dimensions of $(U_\infty T, 128 \text{ m}, 128 \text{ m})$, with $T = 700 \text{ s}$. The additional 100 s are added to get 10-min statistics from the lidars, whose focus point is upstream of the rotor and that would otherwise be out of the turbulent field during the last few seconds of the simulation. The length of 128 m is chosen for both transverse and vertical directions so that we can account for a large portion of the weighting function. Additionally, some distance is needed between the rotor and the edge

of the turbulence box in order to avoid possible biases due to field periodicity [33].

The wake-free dataset contains results from 620 10-min aeroelastic simulations characterized by uniform inflows (no shear). The wind speed varies uniformly within $[4, 14] \text{ m/s}$ to cover the power curve from cut-in to rated values. The turbulent fields are characterized by $L = 29.4 \text{ m}$, $\Gamma = 3.9$ and the parameter $\alpha \epsilon^{2/3}$ is nearly uniformly distributed within $[0.002, 0.25] \text{ m}^{4/3}/\text{s}$. The $\alpha \epsilon^{2/3}$ values are selected in order to get similar TI distributions at different wind speed ranges, with most values between 5% and 20%.

The waked-inflow dataset presents 864 10-min aeroelastic simulations characterized by waked conditions simulated with the DWM model. Three different wake conditions are included: 1/3 of the cases present a centred full wake, 1/3 a partial wake on the right side of the rotor ($\Delta y > 0 \text{ m}$) and 1/3 a partial wake on the left side of the rotor

Fig. 4. Two-dimensional views of the quasi-steady velocity deficit in case of an upstream wake-generator rotor at $x = -5D$ (a), $x = -6D$ (b) and $x = -8D$ (c), with a free-stream velocity of 8 m/s. The two-dimensional plane is obtained for $y = 0$ m. In red we show the weighting function of a CW lidar focused at $(x, y, z) = (-2D, 0, 0)$.

($\Delta y < 0$ m). For each condition, three different along-wind distances Δx are considered: 5D, 6D and 8D, with 96 simulations for each ($\Delta x, \Delta y$) case. Each of those sets of 96 simulations present a uniform distribution of free-stream velocities U_∞ within [6.5, 14] m/s and a nearly uniform distribution of TIs between 5% and 12%. As mentioned in Section 2.2, the waked field results from the superposition of three Mann-model generated turbulent fields. For all the waked fields in the dataset, the ambient turbulent field is generated with $L = 29.4$ m and $\Gamma = 3.9$, while $\alpha c^2/3$ is varied according to the desired level of atmospheric turbulence.

All turbulent wind fields used as input to the aeroelastic simulations are scanned with the lidar simulator to get a dataset of virtual power performance measurements, same as what we would get from a nacelle lidar mounted on an operating wind turbine. As mentioned in Section 2.3, we simulate the lidar scanning geometries illustrated in Fig. 3. For the in-wake cases, we account for the wake evolution inside the probe volume by calculating the quasi-steady velocity deficit at several downstream positions with an interspacing of $\Delta x = 0.1D$ and linearly interpolating for the in-between locations. The wake meandering and the wake-generated turbulence are assumed as invariant with x . From Eq. (3), U_{def} varies with x , while all the other terms remain unchanged. As shown in Fig. 4, we need to account for the wake evolution in order to reliably represent the lidar measurements in wake, as it would be too unrealistic to consider one single profile $U_{def}(x, z)$ within the whole lidar probe volume.

2.5. Evaluation of the multivariate power curves

After performing the aeroelastic simulations and retrieving the virtual lidar measurements, both the wake-free and waked-inflow datasets are used to define multivariate power curves in the form of multivariable polynomial regressions. The input variables are combined into all possible polynomial combinations of degree less than or equal to the specified degree β . For example, for the case with three input variables $y = y(x_1, x_2, x_3)$ and $\beta = 2$, we get the following polynomial expression:

$$y = c_1 + c_2x_1 + c_3x_2 + c_4x_3 + c_5x_1^2 + c_6x_2^2 + c_7x_3^2 + c_8x_1x_2 + c_9x_1x_3 + c_{10}x_2x_3,$$

where c_1, \dots, c_{10} are the coefficients of the polynomial regression.

In the wake-free homogeneous case, we consider two input variables and define the power output as function of the hub-height wind speed (U_{hub}) and atmospheric turbulence represented by the variance of the along-wind velocity component (σ_u^2): $P = P(U_{hub}, \sigma_u^2)$. This choice is based on the homogeneity of the inflow, which makes both U and σ_u^2 uniform over the whole (y, z) plane. For the SpinnerLidar, we use the methods described in Section 2.3 to derive U_{hub} and σ_u^2 .

In the waked-inflow case, due to the strong inhomogeneity of the inflow, all the measured wind speed and turbulence values are considered as potential input variables to the polynomial regressions. When

using lidar measurements, the wind speed U and the radial velocity variance $\sigma_{v_r}^2$ at each scanning location are considered, whereas U and σ_u^2 are considered when using the sonic anemometers. This difference is due to the difficulty in reconstructing σ_u^2 from $\sigma_{v_r}^2$ under inhomogeneous conditions. The input variables are then selected among the measured variables through a feature-selection process.

The feature selection is performed through a forward-selection algorithm. Starting with an empty model, variables are added one by one. At each step, each of the available variables is added to the existing model and the prediction error is calculated using nine values of $\beta = 1, 2, 3, \dots, 9$. The variable providing the lowest error is selected and the selection continues until adding one more variable causes an increase of the prediction error due to overfitting. An illustration of the feature-selection process is shown in Fig. 5.

The prediction error given by each model is evaluated as a K-fold cross-validation with $K = 10$: the dataset is split into ten equally large folds, nine of which are used to train the model and the remaining one is used to test the model. This procedure is performed ten times using each of the folds as testing dataset and the final error, referred to as the generalization error λ , is evaluated as the average of the mean errors from the 10 folds: $\lambda = \frac{1}{10} \sum_j E_j$. The errors E_j are calculated with three different approaches in order to better compare the different models: the root mean square error (RMSE), the mean absolute error (MAE) and the mean absolute percentage error (MAPE). The cross-validation ensures that all observations in the dataset are used to test the model and the error does not depend on how we split into training and test sections.

If we evaluated the prediction accuracy on the 90% training data, the error would decrease with the number of features up to the maximum number of available features. However, this causes an overfitting over the training data with a larger error when testing the regression over the 10% testing data, as the model is too tightly related to the training data, causing less flexibility and larger errors when evaluating on the testing data. Therefore, there is an optimal number of features, which allows the most accurate modelling of the power-velocity relation without causing overfitting, which would enlarge the error as the number of features keep increasing.

3. Results

3.1. Wake-free dataset

For the wake-free dataset, only two variables are considered: the wind speed at hub height U_{hub} and the atmospheric turbulence (σ_u^2 at hub height), as the inflow is uniform and not much benefit is expected by measuring the wind speed at additional locations. In Fig. 6,

Fig. 5. Illustration of the feature-selection process in a case where two input variables are selected out of N available features.

the multivariate power curves are compared with the IEC standard power curve, which is defined using U_{hub} and without any turbulence normalization ($P = P_{IEC}(U_{hub})$). The multivariate power curve is more accurate than the IEC standard when using both SpinnerLidar and sonic anemometer velocity and turbulence measurements, with an error reduction of about 50% from the IEC standard power curve. The optimal polynomial order is $\beta = 7$ for both SpinnerLidar and sonic anemometer measurements. The scatter plots of Fig. 7 show the estimated power against the power predicted by the different power curves for all the 620 observations of the wake-free dataset. As illustrated, the multivariate power curves predict the power output quite accurately, without any significant outliers.

3.2. Waked-inflow dataset

When including the wake cases, the correlation between P and U_{hub} decreases, with higher scattered power curve plots, as shown in Fig. 8. Using the IEC standard power curve results in large errors in the evaluation of the power performance of a wind turbine in wake. Therefore, we use nacelle lidar measurements to define alternative

multivariate power curves, which provide the same accuracy under wake and wake-free conditions.

We train the multivariate polynomial regressions by using SpinnerLidar measurements taken at 2D in front of the rotor for all the 864 cases in the waked-inflow dataset. The optimal number of features among the 800 available variables (400 measurements for both U and $\sigma_{v_r}^2$) and the optimal β are selected through the forward-selection algorithm combined with the $K = 10$ -fold cross-validation. Fig. 9 shows the results of the feature selection, highlighting how the generalization error and the optimal degree change when increasing the number of input variables.

As shown in Fig. 9(a), four features are selected: three values of U and one of $\sigma_{v_r}^2$. When adding a fifth input variable, the error starts to increase and the feature-selection process stops. The input variables are selected approximately along a line passing through the rotor centre. This result agrees with the physics of wakes, which are generally characterized by a concentric velocity field. Finally, the optimal model is a 4th order polynomial with four input variables, giving an error reduction of 59% compared to the case of only one input variable.

We also use the waked-inflow dataset to train and test multivariate power curves based on measurements taken at 2D from the 6-beam lidar, the circular scanning lidar and the grid of sonic anemometers. Additionally, we also consider the case of a grid of sonic anemometers located exactly at the rotor, measuring the flow as if there was no turbine. Results of the forward-selection for those four cases are shown in Fig. 10. In all cases, either four or five features are selected, with three cases out of four including both wind speed and turbulence measurements. The grid of sonic anemometers at 2D is the only case that does not choose to use turbulence measurements. For both cases using the grid of sonic anemometers, the selected features come from measurements at different radial distances, similarly to the case using the SpinnerLidar measurements.

Fig. 11 shows the error variations related to the feature selection illustrated in Fig. 10. For the 6-beam case, the error drops 51% when adding the 2nd feature, and by 55% while including the 3rd and 4th features. For the circular scanning lidar, the five selected features provide an error reduction of 40% compared to the case of a single input. This shows the benefit of adding one measurement at a different radial distance, in analogy to the findings in Fu et al. [30] with regards to turbulence measurements with nacelle lidars. For the sonic anemometer grids, the feature selection provides error reductions of 57% and 52% when measuring at 2D and at the rotor, respectively. As expected, the error is lower when using measurements at the rotor plane, due to a better correlation between the inflow and the power output. As shown in Fig. 4, there might be strong velocity variations within a distance of $\Delta x = 2D$. Although not shown here, in all cases of Fig. 10, the feature selection results in polynomials of the 4th order ($\beta = 4$).

In Fig. 12, the generalization errors from the multivariate power curves are compared with those from the IEC standard power curve, which are also shown by the red line in Fig. 8. We use two different wind speed measurements as input to the relation $P = P_{IEC}(U)$: the wind speed at hub height (U_{hub}) and the rotor-averaged wind speed U_{rotor} estimated as the arithmetic mean of the wind speed values from all the sonic anemometers within the rotor area. As expected, results are more accurate when using U_{rotor} instead of U_{hub} , due to the strongly non-uniform inflow.

When considering only measurements at 2D, all the multivariate power curves outperform the IEC standard. Specifically, the SpinnerLidar provides the highest accuracy with a MAPE of 2.74%, while the circular configuration provides an error of 5.48%, which is larger than that from both the SpinnerLidar and the 6-beam lidar. The IEC power curve is less accurate with MAPE of 24.12% and 12.95% when using U_{hub} and U_{rotor} , respectively. The grid of sonic anemometers at 2D provide a MAPE of 3.43%, which demonstrates that accuracy does not necessarily increase when removing the lidar’s probe-volume effect.

Fig. 6. (a) Generalization error in form of MAPE of power curves for the wake-free cases. (b) Variation of λ_{MAPE} with the order of the polynomial regressions based on sonic anemometer (blue) and SpinnerLidar (orange) measurements; optimal values are highlighted in red.

Fig. 7. Scatter plots of the power estimated by the IEC standard (a) and by the polynomial regression $P = P(U, \sigma_u^2)$ based on SpinnerLidar (b) and sonic anemometer (c) measurements in the wake-free cases. $y = x$ line is shown in red.

Fig. 8. IEC standard power curve (red line) and scattered power curves (blue dots) for cases including wake-free conditions (a), centred wakes (b), laterally-displaced wakes (c), and both centred and laterally-displaced wakes (d).

Fig. 9. (a) Scanning configuration of the SpinnerLidar (blue) with selected measurements (red) of U (circles) and σ_v^2 (squares) in the waked-inflow dataset; numbers indicate the selection order; rotor diameter is highlighted (black). (b) Variation of the generalization error with the number of selected-features. (c) Optimal degree for each model.

Fig. 10. Scanning configurations (blue) and selected measurements (red) of wind speed (circles) and turbulence (squares) in the waked-dataset: (a) 6-beam lidar focused at 2D; (b) circular scanning lidar focused at 2D; (c) grid of sonic anemometers at 2D; (d) grid of sonic anemometers at the rotor. Numbers indicate the selection order. The rotor diameter is highlighted (black).

The lower accuracy of the grid of sonic anemometers compared to the SpinnerLidar might be due to the smaller scanned area; thus it might be beneficial to measure outside of the rotor area. However, the lowest error (MAPE = 2.34%) appears for the grid of sonic anemometers located at the rotor, which shows the benefits of measuring close to the rotor. Similar findings are observed for the IEC power curves, which are more accurate when using wind speed measurements at the rotor position. However, even for the case of U_{rotor} evaluated at the rotor plane, the IEC power curve is less accurate than the multivariate power curves based on measurements at 2D from SpinnerLidar, 6-beam lidar and grid of sonic anemometers.

Table 1 shows all the generalization errors given by the cross-validation over the waked-inflow dataset. As shown in the table, the findings are the same for the MAPE and MAE metrics, whereas a small difference is observed for the RMSE. When using measurements at the rotor, the U_{rotor} -based IEC power curve provides the same RMSE of the grid of sonic anemometers at the rotor and lower RMSE than the SpinnerLidar. This is due to the RMSE giving a relatively high weight to larger errors, as the errors are squared before being averaged. Therefore, the grid of sonic anemometers and the SpinnerLidar give a

few relatively large errors that make the RMSE increasing. However, it should be noted that this is the case only when the IEC power curve is based on measurements at the rotor plane. When using measurements at 2D, the multivariate power curves outperform the IEC power curve for all the error metrics.

The scatter plots of Fig. 13 show the estimated power against the power predicted by the different power curves for all the 864 observations of the waked-inflow dataset. As illustrated, the multivariate power curves predict the power output accurately. Specifically, we have intercept-free regression lines close to $y = 0.99x$ and determination coefficients close to $R^2 = 0.99$ for the SpinnerLidar, 6-beam and grid of sonic anemometer configurations, while the regression is less accurate when using the circular configuration. As illustrated in Figs. 13(a, b), the IEC power curves are less accurate than the multivariate power curves; the former tend to underestimate the power output, with regressions lines in the order of $y = 0.91x$ and $y = 0.95x$ for U_{hub} and U_{rotor} , respectively. Note that for both the 6-beam and circular lidar configurations, although their scatter is lower than that of the IEC power curve, a few strong outliers appear in Figs. 13 (d,e). These

Fig. 11. Variation of the generalization error in the form of RMSE with the number of selected-features when using the waked-inflow dataset in the case of: (a) 6-beam lidar focused at 2D; (b) circular scanning lidar focused at 2D; (c) grid of sonic anemometers at 2D; (d) grid of sonic anemometers at the rotor.

Fig. 12. Generalization error in the form of MAPE given by the optimal model for different configurations when trained and tested with the waked-inflow dataset.

Table 1

Generalization errors from the $K = 10$ cross-validation on the waked-inflow dataset with measurements retrieved both at the rotor and 2D upstream.

λ	2D						Rotor		
	SL	6-beam	Circular	Grid	IEC (U_{hub})	IEC (U_{rotor})	Grid	IEC (U_{hub})	IEC (U_{rotor})
RMSE [kW]	16.8	25.9	33.3	19.2	98.6	51.9	15.6	60.7	15.6
MAE [kW]	10.7	15.3	21.3	12.6	71.1	37.9	9.4	45.1	11.9
MAPE [%]	2.74	3.85	5.48	3.43	24.12	12.95	2.34	15.34	4.03

Fig. 13. Scatter plots of the estimated power against the real power output for different measurements at 2D in the waked-inflow dataset: (a) IEC- U_{hub} ; (b) IEC- U_{rotor} ; (c) SpinnerLidar; (d) 6-beam; (e) Circular; (f) Grid of sonic anemometers. $y = x$ line is shown in red.

two scanning patterns cannot fully evaluate the inflow under waked conditions.

3.3. Combining both datasets

Figs. 6 and 12 show that the multivariate power curves can accurately estimate the power output of a wind turbine under both waked and wake-free conditions. However, those results are obtained by training and testing the polynomial regressions on the single datasets separately, resulting in two different multivariate power curves for the homogeneous and waked conditions.

We want to evaluate whether it is possible to obtain a single multivariate power curve, which characterizes the wind turbine power output irrespective of knowing whether it is in wake or not. Therefore, we combine the two datasets (wake and wake-free) and, then, train and test a multivariate power curve through a $K = 10$ -fold cross-validation over all the 1484 observations. We use measurements from the SpinnerLidar without the feature selection algorithm. We use $\beta = 4$, as it is the optimal value previously selected for the waked dataset, and the four input variables shown in Fig. 9(a), i.e. three wind speed and one turbulence measures taken along a line passing through the rotor centre. In this way, we can assess whether the results from the previous feature-selection are strongly dependent on the training dataset.

When using both datasets, the SpinnerLidar-based multivariate power curve is still accurate, as shown in Fig. 14(a). Compared to training with both datasets separately, the generalization error slightly increases to $\lambda_{MAPE} = 2.86\%$ only.

Furthermore, in order to assess the flexibility of the regression model and its dependence on the training dataset, we use a new dataset to test the SpinnerLidar-based multivariate power curve. Specifically, we use the combination of wake-free and waked-inflow datasets to define the power curve, which is then tested on a new dataset consisting of 192 observations characterized by wakes from either two or three upstream rotors, with a spacing of 6D between them. Distributions for the wind speed and atmospheric turbulence are the same as in the waked-inflow dataset. Here, we do not perform the cross-validation, as

we use the entire combined dataset to train the regression model, which is then used to predict the power output of all the 192 observations in the testing dataset. As shown in Fig. 14(b), the power prediction is very accurate, with a MAPE = 3.42%. The model performs accurately when tested on conditions that are not included in the training dataset; this shows that overfitting is avoided.

3.4. Optimal scanning configuration

The feature selection suggests a common trend for all the measurement configurations: as shown in Fig. 9, the features are selected along a line passing through the rotor centre. Additionally, results using the 6-beam lidar are more accurate than those using the circular configuration, which demonstrates the need for measurements at different radial distances.

In order to test the robustness of the optimal configuration suggested by the results of Figs. 9 and 10, we evaluate how the accuracy of the multivariate power curves changes for different input variables. Specifically, we focus on the SpinnerLidar and use the same polynomial order ($\beta = 4$) and number of features (three wind speed and one turbulence measurements), but selected at different locations. We evaluate how the error changes when we select features along a line through the rotor centre rotated of an azimuth angle θ with respect to the optimal case of Fig. 9. Additionally, we perform the same analysis, but on features over the same radius.

The selected features for each rotation are shown in Fig. 15(a) and the related errors in Fig. 15(b). The error does not vary substantially with the rotations, increasing up to $\lambda_{MAPE} = 4.1\%$. On the contrary, the accuracy strongly decreases when we select the features along a circular path. As shown in Fig. 15(c,d), errors are generally large and strongly dependent on the radius of the circular path, varying from 5.95% to 19.74%. Starting from $R = 7$ m, the error decreases for larger values of R , reaching a minimum at around 3/4 of the rotor radius ($R = 20$ m), and increasing again for circular paths outside the rotor area.

Fig. 14. Scatter plots of the estimated power against the real power output for all the observations of the combined dataset (a) and the multiple-wakes case (b). The power is estimated with the SpinnerLidar-based multivariate power curve. $y = x$ line is shown in red.

Fig. 15. Variation of the generalization error with the selected features. (a, b): Selected features obtained by rotating the optimal locations of an azimuth angle θ . (c, d): Selected features along circular patterns at different radii R.

4. Discussion

4.1. Alternative power curve measurements

We show that the accuracy of the IEC standard power curve under waked conditions increases when measuring closer to the rotor and when using the rotor-averaged wind speed as reference. Therefore, when using the IEC standard power curve in combination with engineering wake models for energy yield assessment, the rotor-averaged wind speed should be used instead of a single measurement at hub height. This aspect is often underestimated when evaluating engineering wake models, where the details are normally put into the modelling of the wakes and not much attention is paid to the wind-to-power conversion [34–36].

In our study, when combining the DWM model with the IEC standard power curve, the power output is predicted with a MAPE of 15.34% and 4.03% when using U_{hub} and U_{rotor} , respectively. However,

these errors are obtained with velocity measurements at the rotor plane. When using measurements at 2D in front of the rotor, as suggested by the IEC standard [6], the error using the IEC standard power curve is much larger (up to 24.12%). Therefore, under inhomogeneous and complex flows, the wind speed should be measured at several locations and as close as possible to the rotor to minimize the errors in predicting power output.

When measuring close to the rotor, e.g. at 1D, one might argue that the wind speed measurements should be corrected for the induction in order to get the free-stream velocity. The need for such correction is a consequence of defining wind turbine power curves as a relation between the power output and the free-stream velocity, which is generally defined as the wind speed measured at the turbine location without the turbine being there. However, wind measurements out of the induction zone are a valid estimation of the free-stream velocity only under few specific conditions, e.g. for an isolated turbine in flat terrain, which do not coincide with the operating conditions of most

wind turbines. Therefore, in this work, we develop a power curve, which relates the power output to a number of characteristics of the inflow without assuming that the velocity measurements correspond to the ‘true’ free-stream velocity.

We use nacelle lidars to measure the inflow characteristics, as they currently are the most capable systems for measuring the wind speed impacting the rotor. The idea is to develop power curves, which relate the power output of the wind turbine to a number of inflow conditions and wind characteristics measured by the lidar rather than to the free-stream velocity. Such power curves would give a reliable estimation of the power output independently of the operating conditions, whereas the IEC standard power curve is reliable only under restricted conditions.

In this work, we propose data-driven power curves in the form of multivariate polynomial regressions based on nacelle lidar measurements, showing that they can reliably evaluate the power performance of a wind turbine under waked conditions. This approach could be replicated with field data by mounting a lidar on the nacelle of a wind turbine, which operates under both waked and free-standing conditions. However, it should be noted that in our simulations, wakes are the only source of flow complexity. Out in the field, inhomogeneity and flow complexity can be caused by a number of factors, such as terrain effects and turbulence conditions. Therefore, more complex methods than multivariate polynomial regressions might be needed to develop power curves that are reliable under both waked and wake-free operation.

4.2. Scanning configurations

All the feature selection processes result in four or five features selected for the optimal model. However, when five features are selected, the use of the 5th selected feature results in small error reductions (2.2% and 1.5% for the circular configuration and the grid of sonic anemometers, respectively). These results suggest that four is the optimal number of features. But where we should retrieve these four features? Results from the feature selection in Figs. 9 and 10 show that it is beneficial to retrieve the measurements along a line through the rotor centre and that measurements at similar radial distances should be avoided. Results in Fig. 15(a,b) further confirm the benefits in measuring along such a line, showing that the accuracy does not change much with the azimuth orientation of the measurements. This is expected due to the shape of the velocity deficit of turbine wakes. By measuring on a radial line, we can estimate the wake radius and the portion of the rotor in wake.

The deficiencies of the circular configuration are confirmed by the results of Fig. 15(c,d). The error is generally large and strongly dependent on the radius of the scanning path. Note how the error is high for a very small radius, it decreases as the radius grows up to about the size of the rotor radius, where it reaches a minimum before increasing again. If the lidar performs such a scanning configuration, the highest accuracy of the multivariate power curve results when scanning at the rotor. When scanning on either a very small or very large circular path, an accurate estimation of the velocity field within the rotor area cannot be achieved.

When using the SpinnerLidar measurements, as shown in Fig. 9(a), the selected features are located both inside and outside of the rotor area, showing that measurements outside the rotor area might be beneficial to evaluate the power performance in wake, as they allow a better characterization of the inflow to the rotor. However, if one had to choose between two configurations presenting all features either inside or outside the rotor area, we expect the error to be larger when using features outside the rotor area. This is because of the order of selection of the features by the feature-selection algorithm, which selects a measurement within the rotor area as first selected feature and one just outside the rotor area as second. Additionally, the circular configurations of Fig. 15(c,d) give the lowest error when using

measurements within the rotor area ($R = 20$ m), suggesting once more that features selected within the rotor area are likely to give a more accurate estimation of the power performance than those outside of the rotor.

5. Conclusions

Alternative wind turbine power curves are implemented in the form of multivariable polynomial regressions, whose input variables consist of several wind speed and turbulence measurements retrieved using nacelle lidars. The power curves are tested on a dataset of synthetic power performance measurements, which is generated through the combination of aeroelastic simulations with virtual nacelle lidar measurements. Additionally, power performance measurements in wake are simulated with the DWM model.

Our results show that nacelle lidars can be used to characterize the power performance of a wind turbine under waked conditions with an accuracy of the same order as that in wake-free operation. Specifically, when using measurements from the SpinnerLidar, we obtain MAPE of 1.12% and 2.74% under homogeneous and waked conditions, respectively. These errors are much lower than those from the IEC standard power curve: 3.07% and 24.12% for homogeneous and waked conditions, respectively, i.e., an error reduction of 88% for the waked inflow cases. Furthermore, under waked conditions, the MAPE from IEC standard power curve is reduced to 4.03% when using a rotor-averaged wind speed at the rotor position.

We test several nacelle lidar configurations, which measure the wind speed at a different number of locations arranged along different patterns. A feature-selection algorithm is used to select the input variables among the available measurements, showing the benefit to measure wind characteristics at more than one location. We find error reductions of more than 50% compared to the case of a univariate polynomial regression using one single wind speed measurement. Additionally, the feature selection shows the importance in measuring turbulence, which is selected as an input variable for all the lidar configurations and for one of the two grid of sonic anemometers.

The optimal multivariate power curve consists of a multivariable polynomial regression of the 4th order with four input variables: three wind speed and one turbulence measurements from different locations. Those measurements should be arranged along a line passing through the rotor centre rather than on a circular pattern to better capture the radial velocity gradient of the waked flow.

Our methodology for power performance evaluation is not largely affected by the lidar probe volume averaging, as the accuracy does not increase when using measurements from virtual sonic anemometers. Additionally, we show that accuracy in power curve measurements increases when measuring closer to the rotor due to wake evolution.

This research might be extended by testing the same approach with field measurements from nacelle lidars within wind farms. Additionally, further numerical investigations including wind turbine induction and wind evolution can be important for future studies.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Alessandro Sebastiani: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing – original draft. **Alfredo Peña:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Niels Troldborg:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – review & editing, Supervision.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Datasets related to this article can be found at <https://doi.org/10.11583/DTU.20156714>.

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